

Amyloxy and Benzyloxysiloxane—Substitutes for Silicones and Their Characterisation

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Amyloxy and benzyloxysiloxanes were obtained by reacting n-amyl and benzyl alcohols and their water mixtures with SiCl_4 in the liquid phase. Their properties, such as refractive index, surface tension, specific heat, coefficient of cubical expansion, silica content, molecular weight, flash and fire points, viscosity and its variation with temperature and pressure, viscosity-temperature coefficient were determined. Based on the experimental data, their tentative structures have been proposed.

THOUGH organosilicon chemistry was developed during the period 1899-1944 by Kipping¹, the importance of silicones received impetus during the Second World War². Silicones have a variety of applications in various industries^{3,4}. Most of the information regarding their preparation and characterisation are patented.

Silicate esters or oxysiloxanes can be developed and used as substitutes for silicones. With this in view amyloxy and benzyloxysiloxanes were prepared by reacting SiCl_4 with n-amyl and benzyl alcohols and their water mixtures in the liquid phase and their properties were determined and discussed.

Experimental

The reaction between SiCl_4 and alcohols is instantaneous and carried out at room temperature and at normal pressure. The detailed experimental procedure is described elsewhere⁵.

The viscosity of the products was found out using an Ostwald viscometer kept in a thermostat and surface tension by burette method. Specific heat was determined by method of mixtures while the silica content was analysed by the methods of Todd and Ridge⁶. The molecular weight of products was determined by cryoscopic method.

Results and Discussion

The variation of viscosity with temperature for different samples of amyloxy and benzyloxysiloxanes are plotted in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively. Increase of temperature decreases the viscosity of each sample but the degree of change differs for each liquid as can be seen from the Figs. 1 and 2. The sample with smaller molecular weight show least change of viscosity with temperature. As the molecular weight increases there is a great change of viscosity. The variation of viscosity of oxysiloxanes with temperature is rather small compared to

petroleum oils. This shows that these fluids are superior to petroleum oils in this respect.

Fig. 1. Plots of viscosity vs temperature for amyloxysiloxanes

Viscosity and other properties such as refractive index, surface tension, molecular weight, molar refraction and silica content of amyloxy and benzyloxysiloxanes, given in Tables 1 and 2, respectively increase with increasing water content in the feed. It indicates the growth of molecular size by the addition of water. The water present in the reaction mixture may hydrolyse SiCl_4 with the initial formation of various silanols. These silanols are so flexible that the end silanol groups will come into contact with each other to form ring compounds with cross-linking depending on the functionality of silanol intermediates. The formation of

various benzyloxysiloxanes (Structure) are outlined below.

As the water content in the reaction mixture increases, it is likely that the resulting siloxanes will have residual hydroxyl groups as shown in the structure. This is evident from the fact that samples prepared with alcohol-water mixtures, especially those with higher amount of water, slowly becomes viscous and gel formation takes place after about a year. This can be attributed to the condensation of the residual hydroxyl groups from the compounds forming polymers. The formation of various amyloxysiloxanes can be proposed similarly.

Arrhenius and Guzman⁷ independently proposed the following exponential type equation for predicting the variation of viscosity of liquids with

Fig. 2 Plots of viscosity vs temperature for benzyloxysiloxanes.

temperature

$$\mu = Ae^{B/RT}$$

where A and B are constants for the given liquid, similar to the frequency factor and activation energy, respectively of the Arrhenius equation. Plots of log μ against $1/T$ for amyloxy and benzyloxysiloxanes are made in Figs. 3 and 4 respectively from which the constants A and B are evaluated and given in Table 3. The applicability of this equation shows that these alkoxy siloxanes formed by the condensation of silanols are only oligomers and not high polymers as this equation is not obeyed by high polymers. Further, the low molecular weight of the samples given in Tables 1 and 2 support this fact.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF AMYLOXYSILOXANES

Sl. no.	Water %	Molecular weight	Specific heat cal g ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹	Surface tension dyn cm ⁻¹	Refractive index	VTC*	Si %	Molecular refraction	Coefficient of cubical expansion × 10 ⁴ per °C	Flash point °F	Fire point °F
1	0	365	0.382	23.70	1.430	0.513	16	87.00	7.90	235	285
2	1	410	0.374	24.25	1.470	0.545	24	103.24	7.65	225	270
3	2	505	0.351	24.97	1.510	0.600	32	124.57	6.73	210	245
4	3	630	0.349	25.31	1.530	0.632	36	152.87	4.97	195	230

$$*VTC (\text{Viscosity temperature coefficient}) = 1 - \frac{\text{Viscosity at } 210^\circ\text{F } (99^\circ\text{C})}{\text{Viscosity at } 100^\circ\text{F } (38^\circ\text{C})}$$

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF BENZYLOXYSILOXANES

Sl. no.	Water %	Molecular weight	Specific heat cal g ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹	Surface tension (dyn cm ⁻¹)	Refractive index	VTC*	Si %	Molecular refraction	Coefficient of cubical expansion × 10 ⁴ per °C	Flash point °F	Fire point °F
1	0	445	0.498	30.78	1.619	0.533	19.66	127.75	6.11	265	307
2	1.0	498	0.467	32.50	1.621	0.545	28.77	140.01	5.86	235	275
3	2.0	580	0.453	33.17	1.625	0.571	36.00	159.94	5.21	220	265
4	3.0	690	0.435	34.34	1.628	0.568	38.00	187.00	4.97	210	255
5	3.5	780	—	35.29	1.629	0.579	41.00	209.00	4.63	195	230

* Explanation as in Table 1.

Fig. 3. Plots of $\log \eta$ vs $1/T$ for amyloxysiloxanes.

Fig. 4. Plots of $\log \eta$ vs $1/T$ for benzyloxysiloxanes

TABLE 3—CONSTANTS A AND B

Water %	Amyloxysiloxanes		Benzyloxysiloxanes	
	A × 10 ⁴	B	A × 10 ⁴	B
0	8.6893	3791.59	12.0785	4378.26
1.0	5.6279	4260.47	11.5478	4576.06
2.0	3.7042	4745.54	11.4118	4733.86
3.0	3.0804	5084.51	11.0787	4979.83
3.5	—	—	9.0698	5269.40

The dependence of viscosity on pressures becomes appreciable from the view point of the usage of the oil in such lubricating systems as bearings. For the prediction of viscosities at various pressures the following equation is used.

$$\mu = \mu_0 e^{\alpha P}$$

where μ =viscosity at pressure P (cp), μ_0 =atmospheric viscosity (cp), and $\alpha=(0.6+0.965 \log \mu_0) \times 10^{-3}$ (ksc) as suggested by Wooster².

Viscosities at pressures upto 1000 ksc were calculated using the above equation for each sample which registered an increasing trend with increasing pressure. From these values the viscosity-pressure coefficient ($d\mu/dP$) were computed and plots of $\log (d\mu/dP)$ vs $\log \mu$ were made in Figs. 5 and 6, respectively for amyloxy and benzyloxysiloxanes. The slopes from these straight line plots are calculated to be 1.028 for the former and 1.077 for the latter.

Fig. 5. Plots of $\log d\mu/dP$ vs $\log \mu$ for amyloxysiloxanes

Similar plot with slope 0.973 was obtained for silicone fluid MS 550 (B.D.H.).

The low surface tension of amyloxy and benzyloxysiloxanes given in Tables 1 and 2 indicates that the oil be of high surface activity. This is a very useful property which helps the oil to wet clean surfaces readily to impart water repellency and release characteristics.

Fig. 6. Plots of $\log d\mu/dP$ vs $\log \mu$ for benzyloxysiloxanes.

The variation of specific heat is insignificant and it appears that specific heat is independent of water content. The oil samples were heated at 70° for 48 h and their viscosity values were determined again. Tetramyloxy and tetrabenzoyloxysiloxanes have no change in their viscosities while decrease in viscosity of the samples prepared with alcohol-water mixture was noted. For example, the values of viscosities of amyloxy and benzyloxysiloxanes are 4.80 and 16.88 cst, respectively before and after heating, whereas the samples prepared with 3% water have viscosity values of 14.50 and 41.53 cst, which decrease to 11.00 and 33.00 cst, respectively after heating for a period of 48 h at 70° .

When heated the bigger molecules may break-down to smaller molecules just like the thermal cracking of petroleum oils. The decreasing values of flash and fire points (Tables 1 and 2) with increasing molecular weight attributed to the decomposition of molecules, lends further support to the above facts. In other words, addition of water to the reaction mixture causes the molecules to be thermally unstable. From the observations it can be stated that tetraalkoxy and tetraaryloxysiloxanes appear to be quite stable and ideally suited for use as heat transfer media.

Conclusion : The properties of amyloxy and benzyloxysiloxanes are similar to those reported for commercial grade silicones, especially from the Dow Corning Corporation. This indicates that these amyloxy and benzyloxysiloxanes can be utilised as viable substitutes for silicones as lubricants, hydraulic fluids, heat transfer liquids, water repellents and mould release agents *etc.*

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